

EURO

European University

FOREU2 REPORT

**CONCLUSIONS ON THE COLLABORATION WITH OTHER
ALLIANCES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF R&I LONG-TERM
STRATEGIES**

Deliverable 2.6

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EELISA Innocore partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

1 Summary

This deliverable has been produced as part of EELISA InnoCORE (EELISA INNOvation and Common Research strategy) WP2 “EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy”, under task 2.8 “Structured collaboration at the European level, among pilot Alliances”.

The document summarizes the participation of EELISA InnoCORE in the **Forum of European Universities, hereinafter referred to as FOREU2**. After an overview of the groups EELISA InnoCORE had an active participation in (section 2), section 3 describes the participation in FOREU2 Swafs subgroup and section 4 describes the participation in the Diversity & Inclusion Hub subgroup and the librarians’ subgroup.

2 FOREU2: Overview

European University Alliances are collaborating and exchanging experience and good practices via fora called FOREU (Forum of European Universities). FOREU1 gathers the alliances from the first wave (first Erasmus+ call) and FOREU2, the ones from the second Erasmus+ call. Within these groups, Alliances have set-up subgroups dealing with different topics, including a subgroup titled “FOREU2 Swafs” focusing on the research and innovation projects of the European University Alliances.

EELISA InnoCORE has an active representation in three subgroups: very particularly and naturally, 1) the FOREU2 Swafs subgroup just mentioned, but also in two other subgroups whose thematic is linked with InnoCORE tasks and WPs, 2) the Diversity & Inclusion Hub (Inter-Alliance Network) and 3) the FOR EU LIB (group for librarians from European University Alliances).

FOREU Subgroup	Leader	EELISA Representative
FOREU2 Swafs	Prof. Dr. Ludovic THILLY University of Poitiers Executive Vice-Rector for EC2U Alliance and European Networks Coordinator General of the EC2U Alliance - ec2u.eu	Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa, Associate Vice-Rector for Innovation and technology transfer, Director of the UPM Technology Transfer Office and Isabel Salgueiro Corrales, EELISA InnoCORE project manager at UPM
Diversity & Inclusion Hub	Melih Özkardes (he/him), Work Package Lead and Ombudsman for Diversity and Gender Equality at ENHANCE - The European Universities of Technology Alliance.	Laura Tierling (from PLS, as leader of the task on gender and diversity under WP7 in EELISA) and Isabel Salgueiro (from UPM, as coordinator of task 1.7 Gender Equality under EELISA InnoCORE)
FOR EU LIB	Sophie Forcadel, CIVICA Alliance project manager at Sciences Po library	Sébastien Perrin, director of the Library at PSL (Paris Sciences et Lettres) and Burcu Bulut, Lecturer, Electronic Resources and Academic Research Services Librarian, at Istanbul Technical University

3 FOREU2 Swafs – Participation of EELISA InnoCORE

In the same fashion as the 17 Alliances from the first Erasmus+ Pilot Calls, the 24 Alliances from the second call (ATHENA, Aurora Alliance, Circle U, E3UDRES2, EC2U, EELISA, ENGAGE.EU, ENHANCE, ENLIGHT, ERUA, EUNICE, EUniWell, EURECA-PRO, EuroTeQ, Eut, FILMEU, INVEST, NeurotechEU, RUN-EU, T4E, ULYSSEUS, UNIC, UNITA, UNIVERSEH) agreed that they would ensure joint collaboration across their Swafs projects by creating a “Forum of European Universities #2 – FOREU” where they will discuss and share intelligence. **The EC2U Alliance offered and has been coordinating FOREU2.**

Figure 1: Logos of the Alliances participating in FOREU2 Swafs group

EELISA InnoCORE has been actively participating in all activities promoted by the group as described in the following subsections.

3.1 FOREU2 Swafs – Meetings

During the lifetime of EELISA InnoCORE, there has been 16 official meetings held by the Swafs subgroup: 24 November 2021, 31 January 2022, 28 March 2022, 22 April 2022 (ad hoc joint FOREU1 and 2 meeting with Stijn Delauré, DG RTD), 10 May 2022, 05 September 2022 (meeting with ETER team, Analyzing Higher Education Institutions through European Tertiary Education Register), 18 October 2022, 06 December 2022, 04 April 2023, 29 June 2023, 11 October 2023, 12 January 2024, 21 February 2024, 25 March 2024, 10 April 2024 and 25 May 2024.

After each meeting, the EELISA InnoCORE representative attending the meeting shares with the other EELISA partners the main messages, outcomes and take-aways of the different meetings via an email:

Figure 2: Example of notes to EELISA InnoCORE partners on the FOREU2 Swafs meeting held on 10 October 2023

Dear InnoCORE partners,

Last Tuesday 10 May, we had the fourth meeting of the FOREU2 Swafs Subgroup. This time, we are sending a long email instead of a report.

During the meeting, Alliances Swafs projects gave each a 3-minute presentation focusing on two priorities and on methodologies/challenges/recommendations. You will find attached to this email and also [here](#) the presentation that we used for EELISA InnoCORE. The session was quite interesting and confirmed that Alliances are facing similar challenges. The recording of the meeting and presentations will be shared. We will send them as soon as we have them.

Here some key aspects:

Research strategies. Logically, WPs of SWAFs projects are all very similar and most Swafs include a WP on developing a common research strategy. In this regard, as [@Nihan YILDIRIM](#) pointed out yesterday, most alliances have done a mapping of research resources very similar to what WP2 is doing. [Here](#) an example from TORCH (CHARM-EU Alliance). [Ulysseus](#) Swafs (Compass) also used a matrix of publications. One difference regarding our mapping is that some Alliances used the mapping as a tool for selecting their research priorities. E.g. under Ulysseus the matrix of publications was tool for the selection of their [six innovation hubs](#). However, Unita run a [Research and Innovation cartography](#) of its three thematic areas, which were preselected in their GA ("UNITA Research & Innovation cartography is a publicly accessible database mapping R&I activities carried out in UNITA universities").

Research priorities and clusters. Swafs research strategies and efforts typically focus on a number of "thematic areas" —e.g. Circle-UE has three "[knowledge hubs](#)" (Climate, Democracy and Global Health), Unita strategy will focus on three pillars called "[innovation hubs](#)" (Cultural Heritage, Circular Economy and Renewable Energies). Sometimes these thematic areas are pre-defined, i.e. they were already in the proposal and in the Grant Agreement and the Alliance has mapped resources in those areas. In other cases, as already pointed out, the selection of priorities was done via the mapping of resources. [@Simona Gallerani](#) **Film-EU is using a cluster scheme that looks close to our protocusters excel** (see screenshot "Captura 10").

Infrastructures. [@Antoine MERCIER](#) Sharing infrastructures with the aim of creating a network of shared infrastructures is also a typical WP and task that many swafs include (e.g. Ulysseus, Unita or <https://theneurotech.eu/>). The general comment was that this exercise is being more difficult than foreseen. **There is a proposal for creating a subgroup under FOREU2 Swafs on infrastructures.**

Figure 3: Notes to EELISA InnoCORE partners on the FOREU2 Swafs meeting held on 10 May 2022

Figure 4: Screenshot of the meeting held on 28 March 2022

Figure 5: Screenshot of the meeting held on 11 October 2022

3.2 FOREU2 Swafs – Reports, position papers and other initiatives

EELISA InnoCORE has also contributed to the various activities promoted by the group, including the participation in other related meetings, contribution to the **two joint deliverables**, various position papers or a document for DG RTD compiling examples of the cross-overs between research and education. Below you will find a list of the most relevant activities:

Date	Action
November 2021	Dissemination and answering to the survey on ERA funding gap and participation in the meeting held on 11 November for the production of "Knowledge ecosystems in the new European Research Area (ERA)" study, commissioned by the European Commission and performed by Technopolis Group.
December 2021	Attendance of the event organised on 8 December to present the draft paper "Reforming the research assessment system". WP3 "EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science Practices" lead beneficiary UPB, represented by Prof. Dana Gheorghe, attended the event on behalf of EELISA InnoCORE.
May 2022	Contribution to and dissemination of the joint statement (41 Alliances) on funding needs including research support "Call for sustainable and holistic support to European University Alliances".
October 2022	"European University Alliances and the New European Innovation Agenda". 19 October 2022, first meeting to present the relevant innovation actions from the new European Innovation Agenda that was adopted in July 2022, as well as the link with the European strategy for universities. 25 October 2022, second joint meeting of European Universities and the Coalition of the willing, to discuss on the possible implementation of innovation actions of the European strategy for universities and the new European Innovation Agenda.
Summer 2023	Contribution to the first FOREU2 joint deliverable on "practices and measures taken/to be taken to ensure the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I long term strategies" , case study 4.
September 2023	Feedback sent to REA and DG RTD on the University Alliance projects. Feedback used for the production among others of the "Report on good practices from European University Alliances Projects (pilot II)": https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/945e39a3-e0f0-11ee-8b2b-01aa75ed71a1/language-en
November 2023	Contribution to the FOREU paper on synergies between Education and Research " Where education and research meet in European University Alliances ". Informal paper with examples on synergies between education and research.
March 2024	Contribution to the second FOREU2 joint deliverable "Report on progress made in the implementation of R&I long-term strategies" .

3.3 FOREU2 Swafs – Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances - Cross-Alliance Forum and other events organised by peers

In addition to FOREU2 meetings, EELISA InnoCORE has also been participating in activities organised by other Alliances:

- ✓ [TORCH Annual Forum¹](#) 2022 organised by CHARM-EU, 3 March 2022, with a presentation by EELISA InnoCORE Research Strategy (~75 participants).
- ✓ [Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances²](#), organised by 4EU+ Alliance, 9 June 2022 (~70 participants).
- ✓ 11th Policymakers Session: [RISIS ETER Dataset, Data and Indicator Needs For The European University Initiative³](#), organised by RISIS project, 13 June 2022 (~100 participants).
- ✓ [DIOSI Open Science event⁴](#), organised by Unite! Alliance, on 30 November 2022 in Madrid (number of participants not available).
- ✓ [TORCH Annual Forum⁵](#) 2023 organised by CHARM-EU, 8 March 2022, with a presentation in cluster 2 “Intensifying R&I cooperation between universities” by Isabel Salgueiro (UPM) and David Schkade (FAU) with the title “EELISA InnoCORE and EELISA Unfolds: opening up our innovation ecosystems, building joint initiatives for innovators and entrepreneurs” (~25 participants in the cluster session 2).
- ✓ [EXPER workshop “Cooperation models among universities: lessons learnt and good practices from European Universities Alliances”](#), on 20 September 2023, online⁶. Presentation of EELISA Networking Platform for Researchers and InnoCORE by Isabel Salgueiro (UPM) and Simona Gallerani (SNS). (~40 participants).
- ✓ [CIVICA Research Conference⁷](#), organised by CIVICA Alliance, on 12 and 13 October 2023 in Paris. Antoine Mercier, Université Paris Science & Lettres, participated on behalf of InnoCORE in workshop 2 “Strengthening Research Management, Capacity, and Excellence within a European University Alliance”.
- ✓ [EELISA and Unite! Matchmaking Workshop on Sustainability⁸](#) on 30 November and 1 December 2023. **Unite! and EELISA teamed up for organising a matchmaking workshop for researchers focusing on sustainability and related research topics.** The matchmaking workshop included two sessions on institutional transformations both Unite! and EELISA are working on: 1) sharing research infrastructures across alliances and 2) setting up alliance-wide PhD initiatives.

¹ <https://www.charm-eu.eu/first-torch-annual-forum-held-successfully>

² <https://4euplus.eu/4EU-353.html>

³ <https://www.risis2.eu/event/11th-policymakers-session-risis-eter-dataset-data-and-indicator-needs-for-the-european-university-initiative/>

⁴ <https://diosi.eu/event/save-the-date-final-event/>

⁵ <https://www.charm-eu.eu/torch-2nd-annual-forum-march-2023>

⁶ <https://exper-project.eu/exper-project-celebrates-successful-workshop-on-best-practices-from-european-universities-alliances/>

⁷ <https://www.civica.eu/news-events/future-past-events/civica-research-conference-2023/>

⁸ <https://www.unite-university.eu/unitenews/unite-meets-ellisa-matchmaking-event-about-green-transition>

Figure 6: Screenshot of the EXPER workshop (20 September 2023)

Figure 7: Screenshot of the II TORCH Forum (8 March 2023)

Lastly, **EELISA InnoCORE** participated in the the [Cross-Alliances Forum 2023](#)⁹ in Brussels on 30 November and 1 December 2023. EELISA InnoCORE gave a presentation in Workshop 1 – Advancing Our Common Science Agendas: building joint structures and support offices, pooling resources, capacity building, human capital, etc. Isabel Salgueiro participated as rapporteur of the workshop during the wrap-up the day after. Sofia D’Aguiar, EELISA Executive Director, and Sophie Griveau, EELISA Dean of Studies attended the forum as well.

Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances - Programme

ORGANISING COMMITTEE

PARTICIPANTS

⁹ <https://www.charm-eu.eu/science-and-society-european-universities-alliances-0>

4 FOREU2 subgroup on Diversity and Gender Equality and other subgroups – – Participation of EELISA InnoCORE

Diversity & Inclusion Hub (“FOREU group on gender and diversity”)

EELISA InnoCORE has also actively participated in the **Diversity & Inclusion Hub (Inter-Alliance Network)** (“FOREU group on gender and diversity”) led by Melih Özkardes, Work Package Lead and Ombudsman for Diversity and Gender Equality at ENHANCE - The European Universities of Technology Alliance. EELISA and EELISA InnoCORE have been represented by Laura Tierling (from PLS, as leader of the task on gender and diversity under WP7 in EELISA) and Isabel Salgueiro (from UPM, as coordinator of task 1.7 Gender Equality under EELISA InnoCORE)

The group held its first meeting on 08 August 2022 and has met a total of 10 times: 08 August 2022, 17 January 2023, 07 March 2023, 09 May 2023, 04 July 2023, 05 September 2023, 07 November 2023, 09 January 2024, 5 March and 03 May 2024. The meetings take place online and are usually attended by around 15 people.

The meetings usually have three parts:

- 1) presentation of the work done on the topic of diversity, inclusiveness and equality by one Alliance,
- 2) presentation from external participant (only in some meetings, e.g., the group had a presentation on “Relevant EU Calls in the field of IDE” by Katja Reppel - Head of Unit RTD.D.4 – Democracy and European Values European Commission Directorate-General Research & Innovation);
- 3) debate in breakout rooms on different topics.

There was a presentation on EELISA and EELISA InnoCORE activities during the meeting held on 5 September 2023.

Figure 8: Screenshot of the meeting held on 17 January 2023

FOR EU LIB (group for librarians from European University Alliances)

The group was launched in 2023, led by Sophie Forcadel, CIVICA Alliance project manager at Sciences Po library. The group held two meetings in March and June 2023. The representatives of EELISA Alliance in this group is Sébastien Perrin, Director of Mines Paris Library at PSL (Paris Sciences et Lettres) and Burcu Bulut, E-Resources and Academic Research Services Librarian at ITU (Istanbul Technical University).

The purpose of this group is to facilitate interaction between libraries on an inter-alliance (and possibly intra-alliance) level.

During the first meeting (21 March 2023), participants outlined their general expectations of the newly formed FOR-EU LIB group. In summary, the group aims to share best practice on a range of topics including:

- how to join and participate in an alliance as partner libraries,
- how to build and manage a network of partner libraries,
- what actions to take to promote open science,
- what actions to take in the areas of information literacy, digital resources and research support.

The group also expressed the wish to have more strategic discussions, for example to address the European Commission through a joint statement. It was decided to create two subgroups under the group which will be dedicated to (1) open science and (2) visibility of libraries in all relevant activities within the Alliance projects.

The FOR EU LIB group was also the trigger for the implementation of the idea of creating the EELISA librarians group, which was first launched in 2021, within the Alliance. It is envisaged that the link between these two directly related groups will assist in the potential implementation of FOR EU GROUP's work within the scope of EELISA.

5 Conclusions

The meetings and activities organised under the umbrella of the different FOREU groups **met fully their objectives:**

- They have been **very useful peer-learning exercises**, where Alliances have been able to learn not only from the successes of peers but also from their challenges and difficulties. Activities have been organised in a way that allowed Alliances and its member universities to speak freely and honestly and, share difficulties as well as success stories. The good practices shared have been a source of inspiration.
- FOREU has also met its objectives as a **networking platform triggering inter-Alliance collaborations** not only at institutional level but also at lower levels. E.g. EELISA and Unite! organised a very successful joint match-making workshop with researchers from both Alliances.
- Lastly, the forum has met its function of serving as a **structured and unified way of communication with DG RTD**, easing communication for both political and more strategic matters as well as for operational and administrative issues.

To end, we would like to acknowledge the effort made by our colleagues in the coordination of the subgroup. We hereby thanks Sophie Forcadel, Melih Özkardes and very specially Ludovic Thilly for the huge efforts in coordinating FOREU2 Swafs subgroup.